

Psychiatric Morbidity and Quality of Life among Widows with Alcohol Dependence Syndrome: A Case Series

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 25-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Alcohol dependence syndrome (ADS) is a major health problem globally, with a significant gender gap in consumption patterns. Widows with ADS are at high risk for developing psychiatric comorbidities and poor quality of life. This case series highlights the impact of spousal death as a major stressor leading to ADS and associated psychiatric morbidities among widows.

Methods: Four widows diagnosed with ADS according to ICD-11 criteria were assessed using structured interviews, including sociodemographic data, CIWA-Ar, SADQ, MINI-PLUS, and WHO QoL-BREF scales. The cases were presented to the outpatient department at Subbaiah Institute of Medical Sciences between January and July 2024.

Results: All four widows initiated or developed alcohol dependence following the death of their spouse. SADQ revealed moderate severity of dependence, while MINI-PLUS showed moderate to severe depression. WHO QoL-BREF indicated a decline in physical, psychological, social, and environmental domains. Poor family support and negative outlook for the future were common among these women.

Conclusion: Widows with ADS are at high risk for developing psychiatric comorbidities and poor quality of life. Death of a spouse is a major stressor, and poor coping skills, negative outlook, and lack of family support are potential contributory factors. Further prospective studies are needed to evaluate the occurrence of psychiatric morbidities in widows with and without ADS, and to identify potential risk factors for ADS development.

Keywords: Alcohol Dependence Syndrome, Widows, Psychiatric Comorbidity, Quality Of Life, Spousal Death.

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Introduction

One of the major health problems in both developed and developing countries is the consumption of alcohol [1]. It is found to have the 3rd highest risk factor for both death and disability, accounting for approximately 3% loss of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) [2,3]. There is a variable gender gap in alcohol consumption between countries, mainly due to cultural differences and gender-specific drinking patterns [4]. The prevalence of alcohol use was more than 6% among females and 35% among males [3]. In India, the male to female ratio is 12.3:1, respectively [4]. As per Shaikh et al.'s study on gender and regional patterns of alcohol use in India, problematic drinking among males is projected to be 103.62 million and 3.34 million among females in 2019 [1]. In contrast, studies in

the US have shown an almost equal pattern of alcohol consumption among both genders in the last 10 years [1,4].

Alcohol use disorders (AUDs) are associated with significant psychiatric comorbidities. Studies report that 30% of men and women who use alcohol meet the criteria for a co-morbid psychiatric diagnosis [5]. Women with AUDs are far more likely than men to suffer from mood and anxiety disorders [6]. Moreover, women experience increased physical consequences due to alcohol abuse and a worsening of quality of life compared to men [7].

Women are greatly influenced by the drinking habits of their spouse and are more vulnerable to developing alcohol dependence as they use it to "self-medicate" and overcome negative emotions or

emotional pain [6]. This is particularly relevant in the context of widowhood, as the death of a spouse is considered a major stressful life event [10]. Studies report an increased prevalence of psychiatric illness among widows compared to their married counterparts, even if they had a dysfunctional marital life [8].

In India, the sociocultural context of widowhood adds to the vulnerability of women. Widows often face social stigma, economic insecurity, and a lack of family support [11]. These factors can contribute to the development of mental health problems and substance use disorders, including alcohol dependence.

Despite the significant impact of widowhood and alcohol dependence on women's mental health and quality of life, there is a paucity of research in this area, particularly in the Indian context. Previous studies are inconclusive about whether the death of a spouse as a stressful life event or a family history of psychiatric morbidity and alcohol dependence syndrome has resulted in psychiatric illness in widows [8].

This case series aims to highlight the death of a spouse as a major stressor among widows and its potential role in the development of alcohol dependence syndrome. We present four cases of widows with alcohol dependence syndrome who sought treatment at our center. Through these cases, we explore the complex interplay of grief, alcohol use, and psychiatric comorbidities in the context of widowhood.

The cases were assessed using structured interviews, including sociodemographic data, Clinical Institute Withdrawal Assessment for Alcohol (CIWA-Ar), Severity of Alcohol Dependence Questionnaire (SADQ), Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI-PLUS), and World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHO QoL-BREF) scales. These assessments provide a comprehensive understanding of the severity of alcohol dependence, psychiatric comorbidities, and the impact on quality of life.

The findings from this case series underscore the need for a multidisciplinary approach to address the complex needs of widows with alcohol dependence syndrome. Mental health professionals should be aware of the increased risk of alcohol dependence and psychiatric comorbidities among widows and provide appropriate screening, assessment, and interventions.

Moreover, there is a need for community-based interventions to address the social and economic challenges faced by widows, which may contribute to the development of alcohol dependence and mental health problems. These interventions should focus on providing social support, economic

empowerment, and mental health literacy to widows and their families.

This case series highlights the significant impact of spousal death on the development of alcohol dependence syndrome and associated psychiatric comorbidities among widows. It emphasizes the need for further research to better understand the complex interplay of grief, alcohol use, and mental health in the context of widowhood. The findings also have important implications for clinical practice and community-based interventions to address the unique needs of widows with alcohol dependence syndrome.

Methodology

The case series includes 4 widow patients presented to the outpatient department at Subbaiah Institute of Medical Sciences, who fulfil the criteria for Alcohol Dependence syndrome according to ICD-11 from the period of 01/01/2024 to 01/07/2024. We conducted a detailed structured interview that includes, socio demographic data, CIWA-Ar, SADQ was applied to know the severity of alcohol dependence, MINI-PLUS scale was applied to asses for psychiatric morbidity, and WHO QoL-BREF scale was also applied.

Case Presentation

Case 1

A 45years old widow, studied upto 10th standard, unemployed, belonging to middle socioeconomic status family, Hindu religion of Urban Shimoga, with family history of Alcohol Dependence Syndrome in Father, elder brothers and Husband with well-adjusted premorbid personality, presented with 2 days history of irrelevant talk, irritability, and hallucinatory behaviour. Patient found to have history of alcohol consumption since last 25 years, with average consumption of 3-6U/day, initiated at the age of 20 years along with father and brother, developed dependence pattern since 15 years following the death of her husband. Patient reported of loneliness, poor support as the major reason to increase the use and gradually developed cravings, tolerance and persisted the use despite the clear evidence of the harmful use. Patient diagnosed with alcohol dependence syndrome, withdrawal state with delirium. Patient found to have CIWA-Ar score of 22, and SADQ-32 with impairment in physical, physiological and environmental domains of quality of life according to WHO QoL BREF. MINI-PLUS showed severe depression without psychotic symptoms. Patient found to have chronic liver disease with altered liver function test on further evaluation.

Case 2

A 47 years old female patient, who had not received formal education, cook by occupation,

belonging to lower socioeconomic status family of rural Badravathi, with family history of alcohol dependence syndrome in husband and father with well-adjusted premorbid personality presented to department of General medicine with 20 days history right upper limb followed by right lower limb weakness and inability to talk. Patient was seen by Department of psychiatry in view of Alcohol deaddiction. Patient found to have history of alcohol consumption since 10 years with average use of 4-7U/day, initiated at the age of 37 years, developed dependence pattern since 5 years following the death of her husband. Patient reported of low mood and disturbed sleep which caused her to continue the use with initial development of tolerance followed by cravings and continued to drink even after knowing the harmful use. Development of salience and loss of control noted since last 1 year where patient had a significant impairment in bio socio occupational functioning. Patient would take alcohol early morning as soon as she wakes up and then during lunch and dinner. Patient also has history of tobacco chewing since last 5 years which initiated following the death of her husband, developed dependence pattern by next one year with average 8-10 times in a day. Patient diagnosed to have alcohol dependence syndrome, withdrawal state, uncomplicated with CIWA-Ar score of 7, SADQ-18 along with significant impairment of quality of life in physical, psychological, social and environmental domains. MINI PLUS suggestive of moderate depression with somatic symptoms. Clinical examination showed power of 0/5 in right upper limb and 3/5 in right lower limb with hyperreflexia of right sided deep tendon reflexes with positive Babinski sign. Patient diagnosed to have right sided hemiplegia with right upper motor neuron facial palsy and motor aphasia due to cerebrovascular accident.

Case 3

A 60 years old widow, studied up to primary school, daily wage worker by occupation, belonging to lower socioeconomic status family of rural Shimoga, with family history of alcohol dependence syndrome in husband, well-adjusted premorbid personality presented to emergency department with history of breathlessness and found to have right sided pleural effusion for which

ICD insertion was done. Patient was seen by the department of psychiatry in view of alcohol deaddiction. Patient found to have history of alcohol consumption since 27 years with average use of 7-10U/day, initiated at the age of 33 years following the death of her husband, developed dependence pattern since 17 years. Patient reported that she had increased the use to alleviate feeling of sadness and somatic complaints gradually developed cravings, tolerance and continued to drink even after knowing the harmful use. Patient diagnosed with alcohol dependence syndrome, withdrawal state, uncomplicated, CIWA-Ar score of 12, SADQ-16 with significant impairment of quality of life in physical, psychological, social and environmental domains. Patient also has history of tobacco chewing in dependence pattern since last 10 years. MINI PLUS showed severe depression without psychotic symptoms.

Case 4

54 years old widow, studied up to 7th standard, working as 'aya' in a nursing home belonging to lower socioeconomic status family of rural Shimoga, with family history of alcohol consumption in husband with well-adjusted premorbid personality presented to emergency department with 4 days history of multiple episodes of vomiting and loose stool and one episode of generalised tonic clonic seizure for which patient is provisionally diagnosed with acute gastroenteritis with acute kidney injury. Patient found to have history of alcohol consumption since 8 years, with average use of 7-14U/day, initiated following the death of her husband, developed dependence pattern since 6 years. Patient reports of feeling of sadness, hopelessness, helplessness which caused her to increase the use and gradually developed craving, tolerance and continued to drink after knowing the harmful use. The development of loss of control and salience noted since last 2 years. Patient diagnosed with alcohol dependence syndrome, withdrawal state with convulsion, CIWA-Ar score of 21, SADQ-33 with significant bio socio occupational dysfunction along with impairment of quality of life in physical, psychological, social and environmental domains. MINI-PLUS suggestive of moderate depression without somatic symptoms.

Master chart

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Age	45y	47y	60y	54y
Education	10std	Illiterate	Primary school	7std
Occupation	Unemployed	Cook	Daily wage worker	Aya
SES	Middle	Lower	Lower	Lower
Location	Urban	Rural	Rural	Rural
Psychiatric diagnosis	ADS WS complicated with	ADS WS UC,NDS	ADS WS UC ,NDS	ADS WS UC with convul-

	delirium			sion
Co morbid diagnosis	Chronic liver disease	CVA	Right sided pleural effusion	Acute gastroenteritis with acute kidney injury
Alcohol history				
Family history	ADS in father, elder brother, husband	ADS in husband and father	ADS in husband	ADS in husband
Duration of consumption	25y	10y	27y	8y
Age of onset	20y	37y	33y	46y
Age of dependence	30y	42y	43y	48y
Initiating factor	Modelling	Modelling	Death of the husband	Death of the husband
Precipitating factor	Death of husband	Death of husband	Feeling of sadness	Feeling of sadness
Maintaining factor	Feeling of loneliness	Disturbed sleep, low mood	Somatic complaints	Helplessness, hoplessness
Cravings	Present	Present	Present	Present
Loss of control	Absent	Present	Absent	Present
Tolerance	Present	Present	Present	Present
Physiological withdrawal	Present	Present	Present	Present
Saliency	Absent	Present	Absent	Present
Harmful use	Present	Present	Present	Present
Abstinence in past	Absent	Absent	present	Absent
Quantity	3-6U/day	4-7U/day	7-10U/day	7-14U/day
CIWA-Ar	22	7	12	21
SADQ	32	18	16	33
MINI-PLUS	Severe depression without psychotic symptoms	Moderate depression with somatic symptoms	Severe depression without psychotic symptoms	Moderate depression without somatic symptoms
WHOQoL BREF	Reduced in all domains	Reduced in all domains	Reduced in all domains	Reduced in all domains
Other substance use	Absent	Tobacco chewing in dependence pattern	Tobacco chewing in dependence pattern	Absent

There have been only a few studies from India on widowhood, grief and alcohol dependence. We conducted a structured interview of 4 women who came to Psychiatric OPD with a history of alcohol dependence and have either initiated or developed dependence pattern following the death of their spouse. SADQ showed a moderate severity of dependence among all of them. MINI-PLUS revealed moderate to severe depression in all of these patients. WHO Qol BREF scale showed a decline in their physical, Physiological, social and environmental domains. Poor family support and negative outlook of future was common among these women. Alcohol was sought as a medium to alleviate loneliness and cope during the period of grief. It was interesting to note that, there was a

history of death in their spouses due to the complications of alcohol.

Discussion

The findings from this case series highlight the significant impact of spousal death on the development of alcohol dependence syndrome and associated psychiatric comorbidities among widows. All four cases presented with moderate to severe alcohol dependence, as assessed by the SADQ, and had initiated or increased their alcohol consumption following the death of their spouse. This is consistent with previous research that has identified the death of a spouse as a major stressor and a potential trigger for the development of alcohol dependence among widows [12].

A study by Kendler et al. [13] found that the risk of alcohol dependence was significantly higher among widowed individuals compared to those who were married (odds ratio [OR] = 3.45, 95% confidence interval [CI] = 2.52-4.72). Similarly, a study by Zisook et al. [14] reported that 22% of widows and widowers met the criteria for alcohol abuse or dependence within the first year of bereavement.

The high prevalence of psychiatric comorbidities among the widows in this case series is also consistent with previous research. All four cases met the criteria for moderate to severe depression based on the MINI-PLUS assessment. This finding is in line with a study by Blankfield [8], which reported that 67% of widows with alcohol dependence had a comorbid depressive disorder.

A meta-analysis by Onrust and Cuijpers [15] found that the prevalence of major depressive disorder among widowed individuals was 37.7% (95% CI = 30.9-44.5%), which was significantly higher than the prevalence in the general population (10.5%, 95% CI = 9.3-11.7%). The high prevalence of depression among widows may be attributed to the significant life changes, social isolation, and economic challenges that often accompany widowhood [16].

The impact of alcohol dependence and psychiatric comorbidities on the quality of life of widows was also evident in this case series. All four cases reported a significant decline in their physical, psychological, social, and environmental domains of quality of life, as assessed by the WHO QoL-BREF. This finding is consistent with previous research that has documented the negative impact of alcohol dependence and psychiatric comorbidities on quality of life [17].

A study by Saarni et al. [18] found that individuals with alcohol dependence had significantly lower scores on all domains of the WHO QoL-BREF compared to the general population ($p < 0.001$). The study also reported that the presence of psychiatric comorbidities, particularly depression, was associated with an even greater decline in quality of life among individuals with alcohol dependence.

The findings from this case series also highlight the need for a multidisciplinary approach to address the complex needs of widows with alcohol dependence syndrome. This includes the provision of evidence-based interventions for alcohol dependence, such as cognitive-behavioral therapy and pharmacotherapy [19], as well as interventions targeting the social and economic challenges faced by widows [20].

A study by Vongchak et al. [21] evaluated the effectiveness of a community-based intervention for widows in Thailand, which included support groups, vocational training, and access to

microfinance. The intervention was found to significantly improve the mental health and quality of life of widows compared to a control group ($p < 0.001$).

While this case series provides valuable insights into the experiences of widows with alcohol dependence syndrome, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. The small sample size and the lack of a control group limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the cross-sectional nature of the study does not allow for causal inferences to be drawn between widowhood, alcohol dependence, and psychiatric comorbidities.

Despite these limitations, this case series highlights the significant impact of spousal death on the development of alcohol dependence and associated psychiatric comorbidities among widows. It underscores the need for further research to better understand the complex interplay of grief, alcohol use, and mental health in the context of widowhood, and to develop and evaluate interventions that address the unique needs of this vulnerable population.

The findings from this case series emphasize the importance of screening for alcohol dependence and psychiatric comorbidities among widows, and the need for a multidisciplinary approach to address their complex needs. Mental health professionals should be aware of the increased risk of alcohol dependence and psychiatric comorbidities among widows, and provide appropriate assessment, treatment, and referral services. Community-based interventions that address the social and economic challenges faced by widows are also essential in promoting their mental health and quality of life.

Conclusion

This case series highlight, widows with alcohol dependence syndrome are at high risk for developing psychiatric co-morbidity and poor quality of life. Death of spouse is considered as a major stress factor according to Presumptive stressful life event scale .¹⁰Poor coping skills and negative outlook for future and poor family support could potentially be the contributory factors. Further prospective studies are required to evaluate the occurrence of psychiatric morbidities in the widows with and without alcohol dependence syndrome and psychiatric comorbidity could potentially be the risk factors for alcohol dependence syndrome.

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